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Effect of intermediate strain rates on shear plugging strength of composites

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Motivation

- Design of light weight armors.
- Ballistic impact on FRP composite plate.
- Generation of longitudinal and transverse waves.
- Generation of shear waves.
- Failure depends on dynamic shear strength.
- Study on the effect of strain rate on shear plugging strength.

Fig 1- Impact on a composite plate

Material specification and preparation

- 200 GSM plain woven E-glass and Carbon fabric used.
- LY556 epoxy and HY951 hardener mixed in 100:9 ratio.
- VARTM technique used to prepare laminates.
- 250× 250 mm FRP laminates prepared with 12 layers fabric.
- Total mass of specimen varied from 212 g to 214 g.

Experimental procedure

- Specimen size 50×50 mm with 11 mm hole.
- Fixture designed according to ASTM D732-02.
- UTM cross head speeds varied from 1 – 500 mm/min.
- Shear strength calculated as- $\tau_{SP} = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi dt}$
- Shear strain rate is – $\dot{\gamma} = \frac{\text{Crosshead speed}}{\text{Clearence}}$
- Strain rates varied from 0.17 to 83.3 s⁻¹

Fig 2- Fixture specimen assembly

Experimental images

Fig 3- Image of the assembled specimen

(a) E-glass/epoxy

(b) Carbon/epoxy

Fig 4: Images of specimen before punching

Fig 5: Images of specimen after punching

Observations

Strain rate (s ⁻¹)	Glass/epoxy (MPa)	Carbon/epoxy (MPa)
0.17	107.6	184.55
8.33	119.8	182.5
16.67	130.5	178.95
33.33	139.0	186.42
83.33	145.6	180.75

Table1: Variation of shear strength with strain rates

Fig 7- Comparison of shear strength variation with strain rate

Conclusions

- E-glass/epoxy was sensitive to shear strain rate
- Carbon/epoxy laminate was insensitive.
- 35.3% increase in strength observed for E-glass/epoxy laminate.
- Strain rate sensitivity for E-glass/epoxy less at higher strain rates.

Thank you

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